

Virtual Tours of Nature: Assessing functionality and usability for fostering nature engagement

Cashel Forest Oak Path, photograph by Emma Sandhu.

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1. Introduction

Increasing use of the outdoors is a Scottish Government National Performance Framework indicator. Encouraging, managing, and investing in this recreation has cross-sectoral policy significance relating to health, environment, planning, education and tourism. The 'Our Natural Health Service' programme and 'green/nature prescription' initiatives aim to integrate the outdoors as a nature-based solution for public health challenges. Related strategies include Active Travel, Walking, and Mental Health. The Land Reform (Scotland) Act 2003 and 2016 provides for responsible access to Scotland's land / inland waters for recreation and education; and outdoor learning is part of the Curriculum for Excellence. Outdoor recreation and its responsible and sustainable facilitation are core to Scottish tourism, and to delivery of the Scottish Biodiversity Strategy.

As increasing numbers of people are encouraged to visit the outdoors, and actively engage in outdoor activities, there is a need to ensure that the natural environments that are being visited are treated in a sustainable, responsible and care-full manner. The Scottish Government RESAS-funded project 'Reciprocal Care for Nature and Wellbeing' is investigating how to cultivate conditions for a reciprocal relationship between people and the environment. This is a relationship that both nurtures the human community through engagement with nature and integrates care for, and responsible access to, nature by people. In one research strand of this project, we are seeking to understand how different visual methods can help facilitate understanding and development of nature engagement capabilities in members of the public. Using literature, existing data, the Scottish Outdoor Access Code, and novel field-based approaches, we are developing and applying frameworks to understand the opportunities and constraints that people experience for engagement with and care for nature.

As part of this work, we are investigating the potential of using virtual tours to help people understand what a place is like before going there, and ultimately how to interact with that place in a responsible manner when they go there. Virtual tours are increasingly used to promote real estate and tourism destinations, and are commonly found in museums as a method of conveying information about inaccessible or ancient locations. Can virtual tours of natural environments help foster a sense of familiarity, comfort, and knowledge about a location – and how to interact with it with care – before visiting?

This report describes the construction of a virtual tour of nature and its evaluation through a survey and focus group. The evaluation primarily focuses on the functionality and usability of the virtual tour. We also, however, report on participants' feedback on additional content they might like, and potential future applications and user groups for virtual tours of nature.

2. Research context

2.1 Benefits of green and blue space

It is widely recognised that exposure to outdoor green and blue spaces such as parks, forests, and beaches is associated with positive outcomes for health and wellbeing (e.g. Hartig et al. 2014; Keniger et al. 2013; White et al., 2020; Yang et al., 2021). Encouraging people to get outside and benefit from these experiences is firmly embedded in Scottish Government policy, and green prescribing initiatives are now established in some NHS Scotland regions (e.g. Marx & More, 2022).

However, not everyone has equal access to quality green and blue spaces, and visits to these spaces are not equally distributed across gender, age, or ethnic grouping (see Colley et al., 2022; Currie et al.,

2021; Boyd et al., 2018). In addition to inequity of access, there are groups and individuals within society that do not feel comfortable visiting green spaces, particularly if it is not somewhere they have been before (Aldam, 2020). There are many potential reasons for this, including upbringing, cultural background, or residential status. For example, Rishbeth et al. (2019) report that asylum seekers and refugee populations can feel uncertain or anxious about using UK urban parks.

In addition to the lack of confidence in engaging with outdoor environments that some experience, others are engaging in ways that can be harmful to the environment. During the COVID-19 pandemic, there was an increase in people taking advantage of Scotland's Right to Roam and exploring areas of natural beauty as well as going wild camping. While increased engagement was widely welcomed (Armstrong et al., 2021) it was unfortunately accompanied by a rise in undesirable behaviour such as lighting fires in sensitive areas rather than using camping stoves and 'dirty camping', that is, leaving litter and human waste (for example, see [Irresponsible Camping in National Park](#)). This behaviour may have been due to a lack of knowledge about how to conduct oneself in a sustainable and care-full manner when outdoors, or perhaps, due to the social context (e.g. peer pressure), people did not feel able/confident to behave in the appropriate manner. It is clearly important to enable people to behave in a way that demonstrates care for nature.

Pairing these issues, we explore whether virtual tours of nature might be a useful tool with which to:

1. foster a sense of comfort/familiarity around an unfamiliar outdoor location, and
2. enable communication and information about appropriate behaviour in that location, looking out for nature while benefitting from being outside in it.

2.2 Virtual tours

Virtual tours are simulations of locations, typically composed of 360° photographs, still images, and videos and constructed in software platforms such as [3D Vista](#). Virtual tours can be enhanced through the use of other multimedia elements such as embedded maps, text, narration, sound effects, and music. It is possible to link to other media platforms and websites, building up a complex resource of information.

Commonly used in the promotion and selling of property, virtual tours allow potential buyers to immerse themselves in a space and visualise themselves there. Virtual tours are used by museums and galleries on their websites to allow future visitors to preview some of their attractions and, inside the venue, as a means of communicating educational information, for example, what historical and ancient sites were like in their prime. Virtual tours are increasingly used by national parks (e.g. Stappung et al., 2023; Wu & Lai, 2022) and conservation organisations and projects (e.g. [The Scottish Forest Alliance](#); [The Woodland Trust](#)) to promote and advertise destinations to potential visitors. Virtual tours also played an important role during the COVID-19 pandemic, allowing people to visit a location from the comfort – and safety – of their own homes (Dybsand, 2024).

2.2.1 Why might virtual tours be good for our research aims?

Our overall research aim is to enable people to understand what a place is like, to encourage them to go there in confidence and, ultimately, to help them learn how to interact in a care-full and responsible manner in that space. In the same way in which people check Google Street View in advance of a trip, we envisage virtual tours of nature as being a tool that could be used by people to see what an 'off-road' place is like, with additional layers of information built in that could be tailored for different user groups (e.g. families with young children, elderly people, neurodivergent people) and focused on helping people to develop the capabilities to engage with nature in a responsible manner.

In the remainder of this report we describe the creation of a virtual tour of the Oak Path in Cashel Forest near Loch Lomond, Scotland. We report on the results from an online survey and a focus group. We additionally provide insight into next steps for this work.

Our initial research focus aims:

1. to investigate whether a 'walkable' virtual tour of a path is easily usable by members of the public on different types of devices;
2. to understand what type of additional content is seen as valuable;
3. to understand whether the tour enables viewers to feel like they know what the place would be like in situ; and,
4. to identify the types of people/groups that might benefit from tours similar to this one.

3. Virtual Tour of Nature: Cashel Forest Oak Path

Cashel Forest is on the east side of Loch Lomond within the Loch Lomond and The Trossachs National Park (LLTNP). LLTNP are keen to promote Cashel Forest as it is currently an undervisited resource that is located only a few miles north of the well-known, highly visited Balmaha (see Figure 1). The site offers similar views to the popular Conic Hill, as well as a range of walks of different lengths and for differing abilities. We created a virtual tour of one of these walks, the Oak Path (see Appendix A for a summary overview of how to create a virtual tour of this type using 3D Vista).

Following the circular Oak Path in a clockwise direction from start to finish, the virtual tour is comprised of 38 360° photographs and one timelapse video. Its design incorporates the following:

- A front page providing both instructions on how to navigate the tour and an overview of the Oak Path itself, detailing practical accessibility information such as the number and types of benches and steepness of the incline (see Figure 2).
- An aerial map view in the top right-hand corner of the screen which indicates current location on the path, with 7 clickable hotspots which link directly to additional content presented on the route of the tour (photographic slideshows of flora, insect life and seasonal differences; videos of badgers; audio recordings of birdsong and burns).
- Links to additional information sources such as the Scottish Outdoor Access Code, LLTNP website, and the Cashel Forest website and Facebook page. These links are available from the 360° photograph of the inside of the visitor centre.
- Information on Cashel Forest's location, parking charges, and visitor centre opening times.

The tour can be viewed at <https://virtualtours.hutton.ac.uk/cashelforestoakpath/>. While best viewed on a larger screen, the tour can be viewed on any computer, tablet, or mobile device.

Figure 1. Map of Loch Lomond and the Trossachs National Park (from the Loch Lomond and Trossachs National Park Website. Available here <https://www.lochlomond-trossachs.org/explore-by-map/>).

Figure 2. Introductory page of the virtual tour of the Oak Path at Cashel Forest, located in the Loch Lomond and Trossachs National Park, Scotland.

4. Methods

4.1 Tour development/piloting

We undertook an iterative approach to developing the tour, which involved piloting versions of the tour with a few individuals, making changes based on their feedback, and then piloting the new version with another few individuals. In total, we piloted the tour with 10 participants. Participants were mainly recruited from the Social, Economic, and Geographical Sciences (SEGS) department of the James Hutton Institute. None had experience of virtual tours or were linked to this project.

We employed a [think-aloud protocol](#), whereby participants were asked to speak aloud while navigating the tour. We also required them to use this method when they completed the draft online survey after taking the tour.

4.2 Online survey

We promoted the tour via a Qualtrics survey which contained a link to the tour which participants accessed after they had provided their informed consent for their data to be collected. The survey addressed general ease of use and functionality; whether people felt they knew what to expect were they to visit the Oak Path in person; how helpful/liked the additional features were; and sought feedback on potential future uses (see Appendix D). At the end of the survey participants were offered the chance to enter a draw for a £25 voucher, and asked to provide their email address if they wanted to be included.

We also embedded a link to the survey within the tour itself, inside the Visitor Centre, for people who discovered the published virtual tour by means other than our promotion (see Figure 3). The online survey was promoted via the SEGS X (formerly Twitter) account so that we could reach as wide a range of potential participants as possible.

Figure 3. The visitor centre (with embedded survey) in the virtual tour of the Oak Path at Cashel Forest, located in the Loch Lomond and Trossachs National Park, Scotland.

4.3 Focus group

We conducted an online focus group to explore usability and functionality of the VNT in greater detail.

Participants were recruited from an Edinburgh-based community Facebook group with approximately 75,000 members, “The Meadows Share”. Following permission from the group administrators to share the recruitment advertisement, we posted on the page briefly describing the project and aims of the focus group, offering a £25 voucher for participation (see Appendix C). Participants were encouraged to comment on the post if they were interested. Twenty-one people responded and all were contacted via Facebook Messenger with further details of the focus group and a request to get in touch via email to access the information sheet and consent form. Seven people requested the information sheet and consent form, five of whom returned consent forms and participated in the focus group.

Participants were required to have a computer or tablet with a stable internet connection, a functioning camera and microphone, and a quiet space where they could participate and not be interrupted. The meeting link (MS Teams) and virtual tour were shared at least one day before the focus group and participants were asked to spend 10-15 minutes exploring the tour prior to joining the meeting. The focus group duration was 90 minutes.

Ethical approval for the evaluation of our tour was sought and granted by the James Hutton Institute’s Research Ethics Committee (JHI-HRE-0143-199v2).

5. Results

5.1 Piloting

The key usability and functionality issues identified during the piloting phase were to do with navigation and wayfinding. Specifically, it was initially difficult for participants to locate which direction they were facing and how far through the route they were.

To address this issue, we ensured that the ‘forward’ and ‘backward’ arrows within each 360° photo were different (white flashing arrow for forward; black static arrow for backward) so that participants could understand which way they were facing on the path. Next, we enabled a ‘radar’ function on the aerial map that rotated at the same angle as participants were facing as they explored a 360° photo, which both indicated where on the route they were, and in which direction they were facing (see Figure 4).

We additionally tried to ensure that everyone was equipped with the knowledge they needed to navigate the tour successfully by creating a front page to the tour. This was incorporated in order to try to mitigate the tendency we had observed in our pilot participants to just ‘jump in’ to the tour from the first 360° photo, heading off down the path without properly exploring that first viewpoint and clicking on the additional information presented there. As one participant commented, it was “*instinct to go straight to the tour and skip the instructions*”. The insertion of the new front page tried to circumvent this tendency by presenting participants with an overview of the tour and detailed information on how to move around it before they entered the tour proper (see Figure 2).

Figure 4. Aerial map of the Oak Path as featured within the tour.

5.2 Promoting an online survey via X: a cautionary tale

We promoted our online survey from the SEGS X (formerly Twitter) account as we wanted to reach a broad range of participants. Although opinion is divided across academics as to whether research participants should be compensated for their time (see Newman et al. 2021), we chose to include this to demonstrate that we valued people's time. All participants in our survey were therefore offered the chance to be entered into a draw for a £25 voucher, and this opportunity was highlighted in our promotional post (see Appendix B).

Our initial promotion of the survey resulted in 136 survey responses in the period of a few days, which was greatly encouraging. However, when we looked closely at the responses, we realised that a large proportion were not from genuine respondents, and that our survey had in fact been completed in many cases by bots (see Figure 5), undoubtedly triggered by the mention of a financial reward. We hypothesised that the high number of bot responses may have resulted from the absence of a CAPTCHA question in our Qualtrics survey, an oversight on our part.

Our second promotion of the survey therefore included a CAPTCHA question. This time we received 348 surveys in total, most of which were submitted within 48 hours of the survey being posted. Again, we identified that a high number of responses were from bots.

On further investigation we discovered that while CAPTCHA questions are aimed at identifying bots, they are not 100% effective. Indeed, there is evidence that some bots are now better at completing CAPTCHA questions than their human counterparts (see [Are You Smarter Than A Robot?](#)).

Given this experience, we decided to eliminate mention of money in our promotional tweet and received only 13 surveys in the space of one week (Appendix B).

5.2.1 Identifying bot responses

Ultimately, we developed a checklist that enabled us to identify likely bot-responses, but the necessity of checking each and every response was time-consuming and less than ideal. Our key checklist items included:

- Speed of survey completion: we judged that it would take a human respondent at least 6 minutes to complete our survey, so surveys completed quicker than this were discounted.

- Time of day: if survey responses had been made between the hours of 01:00 and 05:00 we suspected they were likely to have been made by bots.
- Multiple completions of the survey within a close time frame.
- Email addresses (particularly, in our survey at least, gmail addresses) containing long numerical strings: a rule of thumb is to think about providing this address verbally to someone – is it likely to be genuine?
- Identically phrased responses to the open-ended questions across respondents.
- Unlikely responses to open-ended questions, for example, in our forest-based tour, mentions of traffic.
- Lack of answers to open-ended questions, particularly from respondents who indicated that they had been to Cashel before.

What are bots?

Bots (an abbreviation of 'robot') are automatic software applications that perform repetitive tasks. They follow specific instructions to imitate human behaviour but can perform tasks faster and with greater accuracy, increasing operational efficiency. For example, bots are commonly used in initial interactions with websites (chatbots), to direct customers in the right direction to meet their needs. Whilst many bots can be used for beneficial purposes, malicious or malware bots can be used to disrupt and attack services and organisations, often by spamming and spying. In many cases, programmers/designers of malicious bots are motivated by potential financial gain, so will target opportunities to complete surveys for money or by the mention of a prize draw.

How to detect likely bot responses to online surveys

- Speed of survey completion: has the survey been completed unfeasibly quickly?
- Time of day: has a UK-based survey been completed in the middle of the night?
- Multiple completions within a very close time frame: is it likely that so many respondents would complete a survey within seconds of each other?
- No responses to open-ended questions
- Unlikely responses to open-ended questions
- Identically phrased responses across multiple respondents
- Respondent email addresses with very long numerical strings in them: think about verbally providing this address to someone – is it likely to be genuine?

How to defend online surveys against bot responses

- If offering the opportunity of financial compensation, do not mention it in promotional material posted [online](#)
- Use the inbuilt CAPTCHA question facilities that are commonly available in survey software tools such as [Qualtrics](#), [but](#) be aware that these are not perfect. Some bots are now as good, if not better, than humans at completing CAPTCHA questions
- Build in fake questions to your [survey](#)
- Repeat a question and check for answer consistency across [respondents](#)
- Include a hidden question that is not visible to humans: bots may [answer](#)

Figure 5. An overview of bots.

5.3 Key findings from survey and focus group

After data cleaning, there were 50 genuine respondents to our survey. Of these, 54% (n = 27) were female, and 72% (n=36) were between the ages of 25 and 54. Four respondents (8%) indicated that they had a disability that impacts their use of the outdoors.

5.3.1 Using the virtual tour

Ninety percent of respondents (n=45) reported that the instructions on how to navigate the virtual tour were clear or very clear. Eighty-four percent (n=42) found it easy or very easy to navigate through the tour (two respondents found it difficult or very difficult). Respondents reported using a variety of methods to navigate the tour, depending on the device they were using. Thirty-four percent (n=17) used a phone or tablet, while the remainder used a combination of mouse or onscreen arrows on desktop or laptop computer. Taken together, these findings give us confidence that the tour is easy to use, across a variety of devices.

We wanted to know whether the aerial map was a helpful feature. Of the respondents who reported using the aerial map (84%, n=42), the main reasons included: (i) to figure out where they were on the Oak Path (ii) to check what direction they were facing and, (iii) to jump between hotspots on the map.

When prompted to share anything they did not like about the virtual tour, participant comments included:

- too many unnecessary instructions at the start
- many of the path sections look very similar
- the blinking 'forward' arrows are distracting
- links to the external sites (e.g. in the visitor centre) were missed

5.3.2 Additional content features

Figures 6 and 7 detail survey feedback on the additional content features. The time-lapse video was reported as least helpful and was the least liked feature. Reasons provided were that it was felt by some to be too fast, and to not add value to the tour overall. Focus group participants added that they would like to be able to control the speed of the timelapse, and perhaps have timelapses of areas away from the path, for example, waterfalls, rather than of the path itself.

How helpful did respondents find additional features within the virtual tour?

Figure 6. Survey responses on the helpfulness of additional content features within the tour.

How likeable did survey respondents find additional features within the virtual tour?

Figure 7. Survey responses on the likeableness of additional content features within the tour.

Respondents found the slideshows and wildlife videos helpful. Approximately 40% (n=19) reported that they did not use the links to external websites 'housed' in the visitor centre.

Focus group participants similarly had not used the external links. Discussion identified that this was because it was not clear that the visitor centre was a part of the tour that could be explored. If participants did not choose to move around to the left of the first 360° photograph, they would miss the arrow directing them inside the visitor centre (see Figure 8 for initial viewpoint of this photograph). As one focus group participant explained:

It's just the entry to that first 360 I think is it's not making it apparent that the visitor centre is even something you can go into, because there's this big flashing thing saying start the Oak Path route here and that's that's what you do. You go off, and off you go.

This is a functionality issue that we will address in future versions of the tour.

Figure 8. The first 360° photograph of the tour.

5.3.3 Effectiveness of the virtual tour

Seven survey respondents (14%) reported having visited Cashel Forest and the Oak Path route before. Five of these agreed that the virtual tour was an accurate representation of the path. Of the two who did not agree, one stated “The VR [virtual tour] flattens everything out, no sense of up and down, no glimpses of the scenery through the trees”.

Eighty-eight percent (n=44) of survey respondents said they were more likely to visit Cashel Forest having engaged with the virtual tour. Those who were not more likely to visit gave reasons such as “it looks like many other walks in Scotland”, “I wouldn’t go out of my way to visit”, and “it’s too far away”. This was echoed by some of the participants in the focus group, suggesting that adding more information about what makes Cashel Forest special (e.g. that it’s an ancient woodland) would encourage people using the tour to visit. One focus group participant offered the following suggestion:

What is so special about an ancient woodland and perhaps more about the sort of the ecological processes that are taking place? It could help people connect more with this place, add value to this place and make people think ‘OK, this is somewhere that I want to go’.

When asked if the virtual tour provided enough information to understand what it would be like to visit the path in real life, 90% (n=45) of survey respondents said yes. This same percentage of respondents (90%, n=45) also felt they could confidently visit Cashel Forest in person from the information provided in the tour. Those who did not feel they could confidently visit wanted more information on facilities, public transport, and a map of the location of the forest. This finding suggests that respondents were missing the information point where this is presented (the busy first 360°). Again, this was confirmed by the focus group discussion.

5.3.4 Ideas for enriching the virtual tour content

We asked survey respondents and focus group participants for their ideas about improving the tour. Suggestions included:

- More site-specific information: the history of the woods; oaks and oak ecology; names and information about the insects and plants featured in the slideshows.
- Information about different weather (and midge!) conditions at Cashel Forest throughout the year, and what to wear.
- Precise locations of the benches and picnic bench on the aerial map.
- More footage from off the path, for example, showing views.
- More wildlife videos.
- Videos from different viewpoints e.g. looking over the footbridge at the burn below, to increase the realism of the experience.
- More audio clips e.g. the woods in windy conditions, crunchy leaves underfoot.
- Links to information about the birds in the woods and what they sound like e.g. Wildlife Trust/RSPB websites.

Making the virtual tour a more immersive experience through the addition of more audio and more '*as if I was there*' details (such as looking over the side of the bridge) was expanded on by one focus group participant. She explained how she explored the tour while playing a forest ambience soundtrack, which helped her feel like she was there. She also indicated that she had really wanted to experience the tour using a VR headset. (This is something that can be easily catered for in 3DVista, and we will enable this feature in future versions of the tour.)

5.3.5 Who might benefit from tours like these?

We asked both survey and focus group participants for their opinions on who might benefit from viewing such a virtual tour before visiting the location in real life. Responses included:

- Families with buggies or small children to understand what the facilities and path are like.
- Dog walkers to understand what the route is like.
- Elderly people or people with reduced mobility to see what the terrain and resting points are like.
- People with physical disabilities to understand whether it would be possible for them to manage the path on their own, or with assistance from friends/family.
- People with anxiety, neurodivergence/autistic spectrum disorder, for whom visiting new places can be stressful.
- Preparing school classes ahead of a school visit or residential trip.
- Leaders of groups such as brownies/scouts/school classes sourcing locations for trips; forest school leaders.

- As a teaching and learning tool, to enable people to learn more about typical flora and fauna that can be found in this part of Scotland.

One focus group participant with disabilities that keep them effectively housebound commented that the information provided on the terrain and incline would help them know whether this was somewhere that they could ask their friends to take them with their wheelchair. Another participant, a forest school leader, commented that this type of resource would be invaluable in terms of planning where to hold classes, and also as a classroom teaching and learning tool:

You would be able to explore it virtually and you might be able to make those connections like, OK, we've seen this type of tree in real life in the playgrounds or on our street or whatever. See if you can spot it on this trail. This is what it looks like growing.

5.3.6 Reflections on data collection methods

While we received valuable feedback through our online survey, the challenges we faced in collecting data through promotion on social media means that it is unlikely we will pursue this avenue in evaluating future virtual tours. The feedback and insight we gained through our focus group was extremely rich. The focus groups' experience of spending time outdoors varied, from barely ever being able to spend time outdoors to spending a significant amount of time, even working, outdoors. However, all found there would be a good use for virtual tours in their varied personal and professional lives. Any negative comments on the tour were paired with constructive feedback, such as the additional features mentioned above. As such, we anticipate using focus groups as our primary means of data collection as we move forward with our investigation of virtual tours as a way to foster engagement with and comfort in nature.

6. Conclusions and next steps

Findings from our study have given us confidence that we can present virtual tours of nature using 3D Vista, across multiple devices, that are intuitive to use and do not suffer from major functionality issues. The tour provided people with confidence that they would know what to expect if they visited Cashel Forest's Oak Path in person, and we now have a good understanding of the type of additional content that is seen as valuable, and how to improve this for future tours.

Future directions include applying what we have learned about virtual tour construction and content as we move forward with the next stage of this project, where we will investigate whether virtual tours of nature can be a useful tool to encourage nature engagement among less confident and infrequent visitors to outdoor places. We may also investigate whether virtual tours of nature can help foster and develop awareness of and skills for responsible nature engagement when in the natural environment. For example, we could further explore the functionality of 3D Vista to build in content from the Scottish Outdoor Access Code that can be used to demonstrate, educate, and inform on appropriate and responsible ways to interact with the environment whilst enjoying being in outdoor places.

We will ensure that future virtual tours of nature are viewable with a headset. Not only is this something that some participants mentioned they would like, there is evidence from the literature that positive affect is greater when viewing natural scenes through a head-mounted display than on a flat screen (Yeo et al, 2020; Wu & Lai, 2022). This means that participants are likely to enjoy the virtual tours of nature even more when viewed through an HMD, as well as experiencing a greater sense of presence.

Our study has highlighted some potential drawbacks to virtual tours of nature. Clearly our tour is a snapshot in time: we are unable to show people what the route is likely in all seasons and weather conditions, and cannot, for example, show people a temporary diversion should a path become impassable due to treefall. (Interestingly, the 'snapshot' characteristic of our tour was seen as a positive by some participants. One survey participant who had helped plant trees at Cashel Forest more than 20 years ago was fascinated to see how it now looked, while a focus group participant made the observation that there is cultural value in the frozen status of the tour, that it will be an interesting resource to revisit over time as the forest matures and the climate changes.) The tour is also limited by the route we chose to present: there is no ability for people to go off-route and explore for themselves, echoed by wishes for the ability to pause and look over the bridge at the running water below. While we are now better aware of the types of additional content people would like to see more of, it is true that that a virtual tour of nature will never be able to cater to all the wishes of individuals.

We will further explore methods of promoting and linking external content to our virtual tours. If they are truly to be used as a tool to help people feel comfortable about a place before they go there, they need to be updated with current information, or embedded in websites or well-linked to social media sites such as Facebook, where current states are regularly updated. Although our Oak Path tour had a link to the Cashel Forest web page in its visitor centre, this required active engagement from our participants. Pushing current information into the tour would be preferable: we need to establish whether this is in fact possible. Additionally, it would be good if virtual tour updating became a citizen-science type of arrangement, where people could upload photographs of the location or interesting things they have seen/found on an in-situ walk.

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Appendix A How to create a virtual walking tour in 3D Vista

About 3D Vista

- 3DVista is a software tool that allows the user to stitch together 360° photos to create virtual tours. Additional features include the ability to embed sounds, videos, photos, floorplans, and multifunctional hotspots.
- This software also enables the virtual tour to be viewable in a virtual reality headset, as well as on any computer, tablet or phone (both Android and iOS).

Equipment needed

- 360° camera such as Ricoh Theta 360 or GoPro Max
- Spare batteries
- Tripod/monopod (may need additional weight on base to steady in wind/uneven terrain)
- Selfie stick
- High quality audio recorder such as Zoom H2n with dead cat (wind muff) to mask wind noise

Procedure

- Visit the site and make notes on where to take additional footage e.g. points off the main path
- Storyboard: what footage needs to be captured on the day, and what additional content is desirable?
- Schedule footage taking for good weather if possible
- Take multiple audio recordings at different points along the tour, particularly of water, birdsong, animal and insect life. Edit using freely available software Audacity. (There are also many sound resources freely available online).
- Ensure that 360° photographs overlap i.e. you can see where the next photo will be taken from the centre of the present one.
- Consider taking photographs from different heights
- 360° videos can be good where there is interesting sound e.g. birdsong or stream
- 360° videos can also be used to move between points of interest on the path
- Consider taking timelapse photography where appropriate

Content to incorporate in tour

- Create a floorplan/aerial map so that people can orient/locate themselves, using the radar function to indicate in which direction people are facing.
- Add detailed information on where the site is located in real life, accessibility by public transport, parking availability and price, public toilets/changing facilities, shop/cafe/drinking water, picnic benches etc.

Appendix B Promotional tweets for the survey

First tweet is the promotion of the survey with CAPTCHA and mention of the £25 voucher.

Second tweet is the promotion of the survey without mention of the vouchers.

Promotional tweet example 1:

Promotional tweet example 2:

Appendix C Recruitment advert for focus group

Would you be interested in testing out a virtual tour of Cashel Forest near Loch Lomond as part of a Scottish Government funded research project?

I'm working on a project to encourage use of the outdoors and care for nature in Scotland. We're in the initial stages of creating virtual tours to foster comfort and confidence with using these spaces and would love to hear some feedback from members of the public on one of our first tours.

We're looking for a wide range of people, so you don't need to be 'outdoorsy' or familiar with the area, equally you could be an avid walker and the location is somewhere you've been before!

We're looking for 6-8 people to participate in an online focus group to try out and discuss their thoughts on the tour. This would take no more than 1.5 hours and you will be compensated for your time with a £25 voucher. Participants will need to have access to a computer or laptop and be able to use Microsoft Teams. Focus groups will take place on the evening of the 13th of February or during the day on the 14th or 15th February.

If you're interested, please comment on this post and I will get in touch with you to send on more information!

Appendix D Online Survey

Engaging with Nature Through Virtual Tours

About this project

This project is investigating whether virtual tours of places in Scotland can help encourage people to visit those places and understand what a place is like before they go there. The findings from this project will be used to inform Scottish policy on tourism and responsible outdoor use.

The project is being carried out by a team of social researchers at the James Hutton Institute in Aberdeen (The James Hutton Institute | Science connecting land and people). The research is funded by the Rural and Environment Science and Analytical Services (RESAS) Division of the Scottish Government Strategic Research Programme (2022-27).

What will participating in the study involve?

We will ask you to navigate a virtual tour of a location within the Loch Lomond and Trossachs National Park. The tour can be used on a mobile phone, tablet, laptop or desktop computer, but you may prefer to watch it on a larger screen. The tour should take about 10-15 minutes to complete but you're welcome to spend as long as you'd like going through it.

After you have engaged with the tour we will ask you to complete an online survey, which should take 10 minutes to complete. The survey will ask you some questions about what you thought about the tour, how easy or difficult it was to use, and some background demographic questions about you. At the end of the survey we will ask if you would like to be entered in to a draw for a £25 gift voucher. The whole study should take no more than twenty minutes of your time unless you choose to spend longer engaging with the virtual tour.

What if I change my mind about taking part?

You are entitled to change your mind about taking part at any point during the study, up until publication of findings.

How will we use the information we gather?

The data collected in the project will be treated as confidential. We will not pass any personal data to any other third parties. We plan to report findings of the research in a report to the funder and hope in due course to include findings as part of a peer-reviewed journal article. When we report findings no information will be included that could result in you being identified personally.

Getting in touch

Please don't hesitate to get in touch if you have any questions. You can contact us either by email at Anna.Conniff@hutton.ac.uk or phone on 01224 395394 (Work package leader); Phoebe.Somervail@hutton.ac.uk (Research assistant); Kate.Irvine@hutton.ac.uk (Lead researcher).

I have read the above information and consent to taking part in the study

I consent

I do not consent

Virtual tour link

Below is a link to the virtual tour of an area in Cashel Forest in the Loch Lomond & Trossachs National Park. There are instructions on how to use the virtual tour embedded.

<https://virtualtours.hutton.ac.uk/cashelforestoakpath/>

Please come back to this page to complete the survey once you have finished navigating the virtual tour.

Virtual tour survey

Thank you for taking part in the following survey. The results will help researchers at The James Hutton Institute better understand how virtual tours can help people learn about outdoor places in Scotland.

The survey should take no longer than 10-15 minutes of your time. The survey is divided into 3 sections. The survey will ask you some questions about what you thought about the tour, how easy or difficult it was to use, and some background demographic questions about you. At the end of the survey we will ask if you would like to be entered in to a draw for a £25 gift voucher.

Please be assured that your answers will be stored anonymously, in such a way that your identity, should you choose to take part in the draw, cannot be associated with your survey responses. Your name and email address will be deleted immediately after the prize draw has taken place. You can view The James Hutton Institute's Privacy Policy here: <https://www.hutton.ac.uk/terms>

Choose one of the following answers

Yes, I agree to my data being used in accordance with the information above. I'd like to proceed to the survey now

No thanks, I would like to exit the survey now.

Section 1 – Virtual Tour Feedback

1. Have you been to this location (Cashel Forest) before?
Yes
No [Skip to 5]

2. Have you taken the Oak Path route before?
Yes
No [Skip to 5]

3. Do you think the virtual tour provides an accurate representation of the Oak Path?
Yes
No – Please tell us what we could do to improve the accuracy of the virtual tour [Open text]

4. Do you think you are more likely to take the Oak Path on a future trip, having engaged with the virtual tour? Please explain your answer
Yes [Open text]
No [Open text]

5. Are you more likely to visit Cashel Forest having engaged with the virtual tour?
Yes [Skip to 7]
No

6. Please explain your answer
[Open text]

7. If you were to visit Cashel Forest, would you choose to visit
The Oak Path
Another path (e.g. the Birch path)
Both the Oak path and another path
I'm not sure (Please expand on your answer in the text box below) [Open text]

8. Did the virtual tour provide you with enough information to understand what it would be like to visit this location in real life?
Yes [Skip to 10]
No

9. Please explain why (e.g., I would have liked more information on how to get there)
[Open text]

 10. If you were to visit Cashel Forest in person, do you feel the virtual tour provided you with enough information to do so confidently? (e.g., information about car parking and facilities)
Yes [Skip to Section 2]
No

 11. Please explain what further information would have been helpful (e.g., more details on accessibility)
[Open text]
-

Section 2 – Ease of use and functionality

1. How clear did you find the instructions on how to navigate the virtual tour?
Very unclear – Very clear + “I didn’t read the instructions”

2. Please tell us what method you used to explore each 360° photo? Please select all that apply
Mouse
On screen arrow buttons
A combination of both
N/A – I was using a phone or tablet

3. How easy did you find it to navigate through the virtual tour?
Very difficult – Very easy

4. Please tell us about any aspects that made navigation especially difficult or challenging
[Open text]

5. How did you use the aerial map to navigate the tour? Please select all that apply
To jump between hotspots on the map
Figuring out where I was on the path [Skip to 7]
To see what direction I was facing in the tour [Skip to 7]
I did not use the aerial map [Skip to 7]
Other [Open text] [Skip to 7]

6. Did you find the aerial map helpful in navigating the virtual tour? Please explain your answer

[Open text]

7. How much did you engage with the virtual tour?

I was very engaged - i.e., looked through all the 360 photos and engaged with all information points

I was quite engaged - i.e., I looked through all the 360 photos but skipped through some quickly / did not engage with all the information points

I was somewhat engaged - i.e., I skipped through the tour quickly but engaged with some of the information points when I saw them

I was not engaged - i.e., I did not complete the virtual tour / I did not find it to be helpful or interesting

Other - i.e., I was engaged but only went to the hotspots highlighted on the map - please use the open text box below to explain further [Open text]

8. How **helpful** did you find each of the following features in understanding what you could expect to see from the Oak path? [Matrix question]

Very help – Very unhelpful + “Did not use (N/A)”

‘About the Oak Path’ information

Timelapse video of route up Oak Path

Photos of the woods in different seasons

Oak woods in Spring photo and audio

Photos of fauna/flora

Badger videos

Link to Cashel Forest website

Link to Cashel Forest Facebook page

9. How much did you **like** each of the following features?

[Matrix question]

Very help – Very unhelpful + “Did not use (N/A)”

‘About the Oak Path’ information

Timelapse video of route up Oak Path

Photos of the woods in different seasons

Oak woods in Spring photo and audio

Photos of fauna/flora

Badger videos

Link to Cashel Forest website

Link to Cashel Forest Facebook page

10. Do you feel the virtual tour could be improved by adding more of any of the following features? Please select all that apply

Information points

Pictures

Time lapses
Sound recordings
Educational features
360 photos
N/A

11. Thinking about the virtual tour as a whole, was there anything you didn't like?
[Open text]

 12. Thinking about the virtual tour as a whole, was there anything you feel needs to be improved? e.g. there should be more information about...
[Open text]

 13. Is a virtual tour such as this something that you think you might use before visiting other outdoor places?
Yes
No, please explain [Open text]

 14. Would you recommend using virtual tours to explore outdoor places to friends or family?
Yes
No

 15. Can you think of any useful applications for a virtual tour of this nature? (e.g., an educational tool) [Open text]

 16. Can you think of any groups of people who might particularly benefit from using a virtual tour of this nature? (e.g., to encourage the elderly to use outdoor spaces)

[Open text]

 17. Please add any additional comments you have about this virtual tour.
[Open text]
-

Section 3 – Sociodemographic information

1. What age bracket are you in?
16-24 – 75+

2. How would you describe your gender?

Male

Female

Non-binary / gender fluid

Self-describing [Open text]

Prefer not to say

3. Do you have any disabilities that impact your use of the outdoors?

Yes

No

Prefer not to say

Voucher draw

If you would like to be entered into a draw for a £25 voucher for completing this survey, please enter your email address below.

Following the draw we will delete your contact details from our records. You will only be contacted if you win the draw. You will not be contacted for any other purposes. The draw will take place during the week commencing 4th December 2023.

[Open text]